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S²CIE: semantic, syntactic, and context-based information extraction for AOP development

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ABSTRACT

Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) provide a structured framework for linking mechanistic events across biological organization levels, supporting chemical hazard identification and regulatory decision-making in Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). However, AOP development remains labor-intensive, requiring extensive literature searching and expert review to identify relevant events and supporting evidence. Existing text mining tools often operate on limited datasets, lack interactive capabilities, and miss contextually relevant studies.

To address these challenges, we present S²CIE (Semantic & Syntactic Context-based Information Extraction), an interactive, real-time platform for extracting mechanistic information from biomedical literature. S²CIE annotates PubMed abstracts (32 million) at the word level with grammatical, entity-type, and dependency annotations, enabling custom extraction rules based on syntactic patterns, and employ semantic retrieval based on user specific query. The system supports near real-time querying and integrates entity recognition and visual exploration tools.

We demonstrate S²CIE's utility through four case studies. First, we identified 110 chemicals linked to liver steatosis/cholestasis with 98.79% precision, extracting chemical and PPAR (peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors) interactions as molecular initiating events. Second enrichment analysis of literature derived genes and successful mapping with AOPs. Third, comparative analysis against AOP-HelpFinder for key event relationships in AOP 220 showed 42.2% increased evidence capture (1,614 vs 1,135 abstracts) with 99% reduced retrieval time. Fourth, large-scale extraction of post-translational modification events demonstrated domain-agnostic applicability beyond toxicology. S²CIE accelerates AOP evidence gathering, while maintaining transparency and auditability essential for regulatory application. S²CIE is available as open source through an API and as web application at <https://dev.s2cie.insilicohub.org/>.

1. Introduction

Understanding the mechanistic underpinnings of adverse outcomes in biological systems is essential for accurate hazard identification, particularly as traditional animal testing is increasingly questioned due to the ethical concerns and limited human relevance (Van Norman, 2019). This shift aligns with the broader transition toward Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) frameworks, which emphasize mechanism-based approaches, in vitro assays, computational modeling, and reduction of animal testing (Krewski et al., 2009). Adverse Outcome

Pathways (AOPs) serve as a cornerstone of NGRA by providing a framework to represent and interpret mechanistic information in linearized format (Ankley et al., 2010).

Developing comprehensive AOPs requires integrating mechanistic details such as molecular interactions, pathways and causal relationships primarily described in scientific literature, as curated databases contain only a fraction of this information (Li et al., 2014). Consequently, current AOP development workflows depend on labor-intensive manual systematic review by experts to generate hypotheses and identify gaps. This burden is compounded by the accelerating pace of

Abbreviations: S²CIE, Semantic, Syntactic, and Context-based Information Extraction; AOP, Adverse Outcome Pathway; MIE, Molecular Initiating Event; NGRA, Next-Generation Risk Assessment; NLP, Natural Language Processing; NER, Named Entity Recognition; ODIN, Open Domain INformer; POS, Part-of-Speech; PTM, Post-Translational Modification; SPO, Subject-Predicate-Object; PFOS, Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; API, Application Programming Interface; PFAS, Per, and Polyfluorinated Substances; BPA, Bisphenol A; PPAR, Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor; TPP, Triphenyl phosphate; CYP2E1, Cytochrome P450 2E1; BERN2, Biomedical Entity Recognition and Normalization; REACH, Reading and Assembling Contextual and Holistic Mechanisms from Text; KGX, Knowledge Graph eXchange.

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scientific publication, making it increasingly difficult to keep AOPs updated as the living documents they are intended to be. The scale of this challenge is evident in AOP-wiki (“AOP-Wiki.” Accessed: Aug. 25, 2024); the central repository which contains 556 pathway entries (as of December 16, 2025), yet only 42 have been approved under OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) projects, highlighting the substantial curation and validation bottleneck facing both developers and regulators.

Text mining-based knowledge curation offers a promising approach to address these challenges (Jaylet et al., 2023; Corradi et al., 2024). Several initiatives have emerged to curate event-specific evidence for AOP development, including co-occurrence analysis (AOP-helpFinder) (Jaylet et al., 2023); knowledge graphs (Fecho et al., 2025), and grammatical syntax (Corradi et al., 2024). In parallel domains, methods such as REACH (Reading and Assembling Contextual and Holistic Mechanisms from Text) (Valenzuela-Escárcega et al., 2018) and INDRA (Integrated Network and Dynamical Reasoning Assembler) (Gyori et al., 2017) have successfully implemented structured event extraction for cancer research using declarative query methods. However, these approaches face significant limitations for AOP development. AOP-specific tools typically operate on limited article subsets, rely primarily on co-occurrence without capturing directional relationships, and lack interactive interfaces for iterative curation (Jaylet et al., 2023; Corradi et al., 2024). Meanwhile, tools like REACH and INDRA remain limited to predefined article subsets with rigid query structures that have not been

tailored to AOP requirements.

These limitations stem from a fundamental challenge, capturing the structured relationships that define AOP key events. In AOP, a key event is formally described as a combination of “process,” “object,” and “action” (Ives et al., 2017); a structure resembling subject-object-predicate relationships in sentences. Key events cannot be merely stated as fragments of biological entities (chemicals, genes, diseases) rather, it is the interrelationship among these entities, expressed through grammatical rules in natural language, that provides semantic meaning necessary to define an event. While various text mining tools with named entity recognition (NER) and relation extraction capabilities exist (Wei et al., 2024; Leaman and Lu, 2016; Leaman et al., 2015; Wei et al., 2015; Douglas et al., 2005; Sung et al., 2022) their application for structured declarative extraction in AOP-specific tools remains limited.

To address these bottlenecks, we present S²CIE (Semantic Search and Context-based Information Extraction), an interactive information extraction system that enables researchers to curate knowledge from large-scale literature sources in near-real time. Unlike existing tools limited to predefined article subsets or rigid query structures, S²CIE provides flexible rule and context-based querying that retrieves precise information with granular control, supporting iterative refinement through an interactive curation interface. Integrated entity recognition, and interactive visualization to support hypothesis-driven AOP development. Collectively, these capabilities position S²CIE as a core NLP engine supporting the next generation of AOP. The following sections

Fig. 1. Overview of S²CIE information extraction system consisting of 3 components. (A) PubMed abstracts are processed through customized NLP pipeline (including Named Entity Recognition (NER), POS (Part of Speech) tagging, lemmatization, dependency parsing, and word-level representations). Processed data in JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) format are indexed and queried using both syntactic patterns and context-aware embedding, supported by vector database. (B) Co-occurrence and literature analysis at documents level are supported, where edge provides the literature related information, and nodes represent biological concept with respective ontology. (C) Pattern-based rules facilitate sentence-level knowledge curation, where each extracted nodes (for example a chemical or disease) can be annotated with ontology classes to enable consistent and semantically aligned knowledge representation.

detail S²CIE's implementation and diverse applications for evidence curation. S²CIE and its processing pipeline are available as open-source software (<https://github.com/Crispae/s2cie>).

2. Methods

This section describes the key components of S²CIE as illustrated in Fig. 1. Section 2.1 describes the literature corpus and text processing pipeline that enables pattern-based searching. Section 2.2 explains the contextual relevance ranking system. Section 2.3 presents the web interface for interactive exploration and data export.

2.1. Natural language processing (NLP) on corpus

We processed 32 million PubMed abstracts (indexed up to 2021) through a customized natural language processing (NLP) pipeline to enable structured, pattern-based searching. The pipeline was built using ScispaCy (Neumann et al., 2019), a specialized NLP library for biomedical text, initialized with the “en_core_scibert” model trained on biomedical corpora.

The processing workflow consists of several sequential steps (Fig. 1A). First, abstracts undergo sentence segmentation, tokenization, lemmatization, Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging, and syntactic dependency parsing. These steps identify each word's grammatical role and its syntactic relationships to other words in the sentence, creating a structured representation of sentence grammar. For example, in the sentence “PFOS activates PPAR α ,” dependency parsing identifies “PFOS” as the subject (nominal subject dependency), “activates” as the predicate, and “PPAR α ” as the direct object-relationships that are essential for distinguishing causal statements from mere co-mentions.

Entity recognition and normalization were performed using BERN2 (Sung et al., 2022), which employs a sieve-based approach to identify biological entities (genes, chemicals, diseases, etc.) and link them to standardized identifiers across multiple databases (e.g., NCBI Gene, ChEBI, MeSH). Due to the computational demands of processing 32 million abstracts, entity tagging was conducted as a separate batch process and stored in a dedicated database. A custom NER integration module was developed to retrieve these pre-computed entity annotations and merge them with the ScispaCy pipeline output, tagging each token with its corresponding entity type and database identifier. In cases of overlapping entity spans, for instance, when “hepatic steatosis” could be tagged as either a single disease entity or separate anatomical (“hepatic”) and disease (“steatosis”) entities the annotation with larger span coverage was retained to preserve the most specific biological concept.

To enable real-time pattern-based searching across this large corpus, the annotated abstracts were indexed using Odinson (Valenzuela-Escárcega et al., 2020), a search engine designed for grammatical queries based on the Open Domain Informer (ODIN) framework (Valenzuela-Escárcega et al., 2016). Odinson's indexing structure preserves all linguistic annotations (POS tags, dependencies, entity types) while enabling fast retrieval through optimized data structures. Query response times and scalability analysis are provided in Supplementary Section 2.

For indexing, processed documents were compiled into JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) format, a structured data format that preserves the hierarchical organization of documents, sentences, and words. Each document is decomposed into sentences, and each sentence is represented as an ordered array of words (tokens). Every token is annotated with multiple fields: “tag” (POS tag), “lemma” (base word form), “entity” (biological entity type and identifier), “chunk” (phrase membership), and “norm” (normalized form). Additionally, tokens are annotated with incoming and outgoing dependency arcs (grammatical relationships), forming a dependency graph for each sentence. This rich annotation structure enables declarative rule-based querying, where users can specify patterns that match not only lexical content (specific words) but also grammatical structure (e.g., “find sentences where a

[chemical entity] is the subject of the verb ‘activate’ with a [gene entity] as the direct object”). The structured query syntax is detailed in Supplementary Section 1.

2.2. Context search integration

While pattern-based queries (Section 2.1) enable precise extraction of specific grammatical relationships, they may miss relevant articles that describe similar concepts using different terminology. To address this limitation, S²CIE integrates semantic similarity ranking that complements pattern-based searching by identifying conceptually related articles even when exact terminology differs. Recent advances in natural language processing have demonstrated that such dense semantic representations achieve more effective retrieval of conceptually related content compared to traditional keyword-based methods (Jin, 2023).

Embedding models are typically built on pre-trained transformer architectures and fine-tuned for specific tasks. However, models trained on general text corpora often fail to capture domain-specific terminology and relationships in specialized fields like toxicology and pharmacology (Gu, et al., 2022). We therefore employed MedCPT (bioMedical Contrastive Pre-trained Transformers) (Jin, 2023) an open-source model specifically fine-tuned on 255 million query-article pairs derived from actual PubMed search logs (2020–2022). This training data reflects real information-seeking behaviour by biomedical researchers, ensuring the model understands domain-specific semantic relationships. MedCPT's retriever component is initialized with PubMedBERT (Gu, et al., 2022) a language model pre-trained on biomedical literature, providing an inherent understanding of biological and chemical terminology and contextual nuances in scientific articles.

To enable real-time contextual ranking without computational delays, we employ a two-stage architecture. First, embeddings for all 32 million abstracts were pre-computed offline and stored in a database indexed by PubMed ID. During query execution, only the user's query text is encoded (a fast operation taking < 1 s), and its embedding is compared against the stored article embeddings from the initial pattern-based results. This comparison uses cosine similarity to identify the most semantically relevant articles, which are then ranked accordingly. The system uses FAISS (Facebook AI Similarity Search) (Johnson et al., 2017), an optimized library for efficient similarity search in high-dimensional vector spaces, enabling rapid re-ranking of retrieved article sets based on contextual relevance.

2.3. S²CIE search interface

S²CIE is accessible at <https://dev.s2cie.insilicohub.org>. The web user interface is organized into three main sections: 1) search, 2) results and 3) entities filtering (Fig. 2). For lexical and syntactic searches, users can choose between two modes: “Basic” search for direct queries and “Grammar” search for nested patterns. A detailed syntax guide with examples is provided in supplementary Section 1. The “Context” search option enables relevance-based filtering by ranking a subset of the abstracts based on the semantic similarity to the user specified query. Search results are presented as a ranked list of matching sentences along with PMIDs. Users can interact with the results by upvoting and downvoting sentences based on their relevance. Search results can be downloaded in CSV (Comma Separated Value) format, containing PMIDs, sentence ID, sentences and scores allowing usage for downstream application. The right pane of the interface displays biological concepts extracted from abstracts, allowing users to filter results based on specific entity mentions. Captured terms defined in the query as a placeholder are stored under the “capture” tab. The “Visualization” tab supports data exploration through plots, heatmaps and network diagram (Fig. 1B), enabling users to analyse the distribution and co-occurrence of biological concepts. Co-occurrence visualizations are supported by integration with Cystoscape (Franz et al., 2016). S²CIE serves as an evidence curation tool for AOP developers and regulatory risk assessment.

Fig. 2. S²CIE web interface overview. The platform supports three search modes with increasing specificity: (1) Basic Search using pattern-matching with usage examples shown, (2) Grammar Search enabling custom dependency-based queries, and (3) Context Search for semantic filtering and ranking of results. The right panel provides entity-type filters (Gene, Chemical, Disease, etc.) and downstream analysis tools including network visualization and pathway analysis of co-occurrence patterns.

The system provides RESTful API access for programmatic integration with existing workflows and can be deployed within AOP-Wiki as a third-party application, facilitating systematic literature-based evidence gathering for adverse outcome pathway development.

3. Case studies with S²CIE

We conducted four case studies evaluating S²CIE: (1) identifying chemical stressors for cholestasis/steatosis and their PPAR interactions, (2) enrichment analysis and AOP mapping of literature-derived genes, (3) benchmarking against AOP-helpFinder for AOP 220 (“Adverse Outcome Pathway on Cyp2E1 activation leading to liver cancer,” 2021); and (4) large-scale post-translational modification extraction demonstrating domain-agnostic applicability.

3.1. Case study 1: Exploring causal chemical interactions in steatosis and cholestasis

Although AOPs describe stressor-agnostic biological pathways (Villeneuve et al., 2014); their practical application in risk assessment requires identifying which chemicals can trigger specific AOPs and characterizing their mechanisms at the molecular initiating event (MIE) level. This case study explores a) chemicals inducing steatosis/cholestasis, and b) evidence of chemical PPAR interactions as the initiating event.

Study 3.1.1: Identifying chemicals leading to steatosis or cholestasis

We extracted evidence for chemicals inducing steatosis or cholestasis as target adverse outcomes for liver disease. Using AOP-wiki explorer (Kumar et al., 2024), 16 chemical entities (Fig. S1) associated with liver disease were identified. Most of these chemical mentioned were embedded within unstructured text in the AOP-wiki rather than catalogued in structured fields. Notably, a few well-defined stressors were listed, including “PPARalpha antagonists”, “Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)”, “Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances (PFAS)”, “PPAR agonist”, and “*Helicobacter pylori*” (a biological stressor, noted as an exception to the chemical focus of this study). To create a more

comprehensive chemical landscape, we complemented this with systematic literature extraction using S²CIE.

Using S²CIE Subject-Predicate-Object (SPO) query patterns, that capture relationships between subject and object in natural language sentences (Table S1). We extracted direct evidence from the literature linking specific chemicals to the induction of cholestasis/steatosis (Corradi et al., 2024). While co-occurrence based extraction is supported by S²CIE, we restricted this case study to direct evidence to ensure higher precision. S²CIE identified 110 chemicals entities ranging from atomic elements (manganese, aluminium) to long-chain fatty acid (palmitoleate) and herbal extracts, classified as either activator or inhibitors of steatosis/cholestasis (Fig. 3).

Manual validation by domain experts (Supplementary Data File) confirmed high extraction accuracy: 101/102 steatosis entries (99.01 %) and 63/64 cholestasis entries (98.43 %) were correct, achieving overall precision of 98.79 %. Misclassification occurred when: (i) “triglyceride” was incorrectly identified as a chemical stressor instead of the R(-) and S-(+) enantiomeric forms of ibuprofen, and (ii) for cholestasis, when evidence sentences contained both main and subordinate clauses, the extraction patterns successfully captured information from the main clause but missed relevant information from the subordinate clause. Additionally, chemicals mentioned adjacent to target entities were sometimes not captured, as extraction patterns did not account for positional dependencies. Negated sentences were effectively filtered out using dependency graph patterns (the negation dependency >/neg/).

Among the identified chemicals, such as BPA (Bisphenol A), and PFOS (Perfluorooctane-1-sulfonic acids) were classified as steatosis activators, while inhibitors included statins (pitavastatin, lovastatin, rosuvastatin), natural compounds (ajoene, naringin, lycopene). Ethanol emerged as the most frequently observed chemical, appearing 17 times (Fig. S2), followed by 17alpha-Ethinylestradiol, Taurolithocholate, Alpha-naphthylisothiocyanate, perfluorooctane-1-sulfonic acid, and dexamethasone, each occurring with a frequency of 4. The chemicals extracted with S²CIE provides a literature-derived evidence base that can (i) assist researchers in prioritizing chemicals for targeted experimental validation, and (ii) facilitate mechanistic interpretation at the

Fig. 3. Network visualizations of chemical-disease relationships for steatosis (A) and cholestasis (B). Chemicals (peripheral nodes) connect to the central disease node through literature-derived relationships. Edge colors indicate interaction type: orange for activators (causes, induces, produces, increases) and red for inhibitors (inhibits, diminished). The steatosis network comprises 67 chemicals with 102 evidence statements; cholestasis contains 43 chemicals with 64 statements. Detailed evidence with document IDs and source sentences available in Supplementary excel file (tabs: “steatosisEvidences” and “cholestasisEvidences”).

molecular initiating event (MIE) level. In particular, the identified chemical-MIE associations can be further explored using cheminformatics approaches such as molecular docking, to probe potential interaction sites and binding mechanisms. This approach was demonstrated in AOP 423 (“AOP-Wiki.” Accessed: Nov. 13, 2025), where molecular docking was used to investigate the interaction between Triphenyl phosphate (TPP) and PARR1 and in similar pipelines implemented by Jeong et. al (Jeong et al., 2023). and Ortega-vallbona et. al (Ortega-Vallbona et al., 2025).

As a downstream analysis (supplementary section 3) on curated chemicals from literature, we examined the substructural similarities among steatosis associated compounds using Morgan fingerprints and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). This circular fingerprinting approach captures molecular substructures as numerical identifiers, enabling quantitative structural comparisons. PCA revealed distinct clustering patterns (Fig. S6): activators like PFOS and BPA formed dense clusters, indicating shared substructural features that may mediate similar receptor interactions as activator at the MIE level. In contrast, statin inhibitors (rosuvastatin, pitavastatin) appeared as outliers with unique structural signatures, suggesting distinct mechanisms of action. Other structurally diverse inhibitors, including naringin and ajoene, were sparsely distributed across the PCA space, further supporting heterogeneity among steatosis inhibitors.

Study 3.1.2: Chemical and receptor interaction for steatosis and cholestasis

The second component of this case study focused on targeting events focused on interaction with PPARs. For extracting evidence of chemical PPAR binding or interaction, we used SPO query patterns where the object was restricted to “PPAR” while the subject matched any noun-tagged token (capturing both named entities and general nouns), and the predicate matched any verb. This flexible annotation strategy enables capture of diverse relationship types (e.g., “activates,” “binds to,” “inhibits”) in resource-constrained settings where comprehensive relationship ontologies may not exist. The query pattern used was:

```
(?<subject > [tag=/N.*/] < nsubj (?<predicate > [tag=/V.*/] >
dobj (?<object > [lemma=/ppar/])
```

Overall, 529 evidence (Supplementary Data File [tab: PPAREvents]) were obtained which were further filtered to retain only those sentences (Table S2) referring to chemicals mentioned in Section 3.1.1. We then applied context search to score the evidence, to identify sentences mentioning exact chemicals or closely related compounds.

The contextual ranking demonstrated valuable chemical discovery capabilities. For instance, querying “PFOS” also returned sentences mentioning PFOA, APFO and PFAAs, all chemically related perfluorinated compounds. Similarly, PBDE was retrieved when searching for BPA due to their shared endocrine-disrupting properties. For inhibitors, context-based scoring prioritized norbixin when querying “lycopene,” as both belong to the carotenoid family. Likewise, apigenin was identified as related to genistein through their shared classification as flavonoids. Querying “fenofibrate,” a known PPAR-alpha agonist used therapeutically, also retrieved “clofibrate” and “bezafibrate,” both PPAR-alpha agonists. Fecho et al. identified similar mechanistic relationships for fibrates and liver diseases using the ROBOKOP knowledge graph as an information discovery process (Fecho et al., 2025). These findings implies that interaction with PPAR is not sufficient to induce steatosis, a hypothesis that requires further validation through experimental studies. Several chemicals classified as inhibitors also activate PPAR alpha but do not cause adverse outcomes; instead, they may mitigate such effects. For example, lycopene and its derivative norbixin, as well as flavonoids such as genistein and apigenin, activate PPAR alpha yet are associated with the inhibition of steatosis (Ip et al., 2015). Similarly, fibrates (fenofibrate, clofibrate, and bezafibrate), although PPAR-alpha agonists are reported to ameliorate liver conditions (Tanaka; Won, 2013). In conclusion, while PPAR alpha activation is frequently observed among steatosis-inducing chemicals, not all activators ultimately lead to steatosis. The downstream effect likely depends on additional pathways and events modulated by these compounds, highlighting the importance of key event relationships in AOP frameworks.

The S²CIE extraction patterns are highly flexible. Users can adjust query specificity depending on their evidence requirements. For instance, to extract broader evidence of how PPAR leads to steatosis, queries can be modified to capture subject-object relationships where PPAR appears anywhere in the sentence rather than as a direct grammatical object (examples in Table 1). Additional query patterns for extracting key event relationships in AOP 529 are detailed in supplementary section 4 and Table S8 of the supplementary material.

3.2. Case study 2: pathway and process enrichment of literature-derived genes

To demonstrate S²CIE’s utility for downstream bioinformatics, we

Table 1

Rules used to extract evidence for PPAR and its role in steatosis. The rules differ in their constraints: the first rule follows the dependency graph pattern and yielded 70 statements, whereas the second rule, based on co-occurrence patterns, extracted 170 statements.

Rules	Explanation	Statement count
(?<subject > [lemma=/ppar/]) []*? (?<relation > [tag=/V. */]) > dobj (?<object > [lemma=/steatosis cholestasis/])	Existence of ppar and steatosis in a single sentence, where steatosis is linked with verbs	70
(?<subject > [lemma=/ppar/]) []*? (?<relation > [tag=/V. */]) []*? (?<object > [lemma=/steatosis cholestasis/])	Existence of ppar and steatosis in a single sentence, where verb mentioned in between them.	170

extracted genes associated with steatosis or cholestasis initiation. Following expert validation (Supplementary Data File [Tabs: SteatosisGene]), genes with direct roles in liver disease (mentioned ≥ 5 times) were functionally annotated using KEGG pathways, GO Biological Process, and GO Molecular Function via G:Profiler (Raudvere et al., 2019) (p-value < 0.05; Fig. 4).

1. KEGG Pathway Analysis. KEGG enrichment (Fig. 4A) identified AMPK and PPAR signaling pathways as major regulators of fat and glucose metabolism. Disease-specific pathways included “Alcoholic liver disease” and “Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD),” alongside metabolically relevant processes such as insulin resistance, cholesterol metabolism, and fatty acid metabolism. The presence of both alcoholic and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease pathways

indicates strong interconnections between liver-centric metabolic diseases.

2. GO Biological Process. The most significantly enriched biological process was “lipid metabolic process” (GO:0006629), followed by “positive regulation of lipid metabolic process” (GO:0045834). Additional enriched processes (GO:0019915, GO:0055088, GO:0006631, GO:0009245) were predominantly lipid-associated, reflecting the central role of these genes in liver pathology (Fig. 4C).

3. GO Molecular Function. Molecular function analysis (Fig. 4B) revealed “nuclear receptor activity” and “ligand-activated transcription factor activity” as the most significant terms. PPARs and PXR, both ligand-activated nuclear receptors with ligand and DNA-binding domains, function as chemical-responsive switches. These receptors appear primarily as molecular initiating events in AOPs 36, 58, 60, 517, and 529, where stressor binding initiates the pathway. Other enriched terms “lipid transporter activity,” “cholesterol transfer activity,” and “acyltransferase activity” are directly involved in lipid transport and modification.

All three analyses converge on lipid metabolism, its regulation, and associated metabolic diseases as central themes in steatosis/cholestasis pathogenesis. We successfully mapped the identified processes to existing AOPs using genes documented in AOP-wiki (Fig. 5; Table S3).

Methodological Observation: Notably, current key event GO annotations predominantly use broad, high-level terms such as “signaling” (GO:0023052) and “gene expression” (GO:0010467) (Fig. S3). These general annotations limit computational utility for automated inference and mechanistic gap identification. More specific, lower-level GO terms would improve pathway identification precision and reduce search space.

Fig. 4. Pathway and functional enrichment analysis of genes derived from literature related to liver disease. A.) KEGG pathway enrichment showing the top 10 significantly enriched pathways (p < 0.05), including AMPK signaling, PPAR signaling, and pathways involved in lipid metabolism and liver disorders. B.) GO Molecular Function (GO:MF) enrichment highlighting top functional terms such as nuclear receptor activity, lipid binding, and acyltransferase activity. C.) GO Biological Process (GO:BP) enrichment illustrating key biological processes including lipid metabolic process, lipid storage, and regulation of lipid homeostasis.

Fig. 5. Heatmap visualization of GO biological process associations with identified genes through S²CIE and their mapping across multiple Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs). The heatmap includes 10 biological processes and 21 genes. The “lipid metabolic process” showed the highest number of associations with the identified genes and was linked with AOPs such as 34, 61, 58, 318. Genes with the broadest associations across multiple GO terms include SREBF1, HMGCR, SCAP, FASN, DGAT1, and PPARA, which frequently show involvement in multiple AOPs (indicated by black outlines). AOP 34 (red) was the most prevalent, associated with numerous gene-GO term relationships. Other AOP associations include AOP 61 (blue) with NR1H4, APOB, MTTP; AOP 58 (cyan) with CD36; and AOP 318 (magenta) with ACOX1. Refer table S3 for detailed mapping.

3.3. Case study 3: key event relationships extraction for AOP 220

To evaluate S²CIE’s evidence extraction performance, we compared it against AOP-HelpFinder v2 for extracting key event relationships in AOP 220 (CYP2E1 Activation Leading to Liver Cancer). We compared the number of extracted relationships across nine key event pairs in AOP

220 (Fig. 6). Overall, S²CIE extracted 1,614 total evidence instances compared to 1,135 from AOP-HelpFinder v2, representing a 42.2 % increase in evidence capture (Supplementary Data File). This significant increase can be attributed to the following features of S²CIE:

Comparison of Result Counts: S²CIE vs AOP Helpfinder

Fig. 6. Comparative evidence extraction performance of S²CIE and AOP-HelpFinder for AOP 220 (Cyp2E1 Activation Leading to Liver Cancer). S²CIE (blue) extracted 42.2% more evidence than AOP-HelpFinder (red) across all event pairs (1,614 vs 1,135 abstracts). Numbers indicate abstract count for each relationship.

1. Real-time feedback of query, which let users experiment with different queries on the entire corpus in with near real-time experience. AOP-helpFinder v2 evaluated their system on entire PubMed (35 million, 2023 indexed) on all above 9 key event it takes “11 hrs” and “26 min” on their pre-selected abstracts (733,413 abstracts) (Jaylet et al., 2023). Whereas S²CIE in their worst scenario (no constrain) can perform extraction on average within 3.36 min (Table S7) achieving approximately 99 % reduction in retrieval time.
2. AOP-helpfinder’s NLP pipeline limits word matching to stemmed forms with limited variations, making results sensitive to how events are phrased, for instance, “Cyp2E1 activation” and “Cyp2E1 induction” are treated differently despite representing similar biological processes (Jaylet et al., 2023). In contrast, S²CIE provides access to multiple matching fields (word, lemma, tag, entity type) and supports regular expressions and quantifiers, allowing users to capture semantic equivalents systematically. For example, the query [lemma=/cyp2e1/](?=/activ.*|induc.*/) captures all variations of both “activation” and “induction” in a single search pattern, enabling

more comprehensive evidence extraction regardless of terminology variations used across different publications.

3. Transparency in the response, result provided to the user is the direct sentences that match the pattern, allowing users to validate whether this is desired response or not. The uniform pattern syntax applies to both single events and multiple cascading events such as key event relationship, giving users granular control over the NLP pipeline.

The performance differences varied considerably across key event pairs. S²CIE demonstrated particularly strong performance in extracting evidence for “Oxidative stress → Hepatotoxicity” (1,072 vs 753 abstracts) and “Oxidative stress → Increased proliferation” (258 vs 178 abstracts) because of variations provided within keywords and use of look forward and regex like query pattern. For relationships involving hepatotoxicity as the upstream event, S²CIE showed even more pronounced advantages: “Hepatotoxicity → Liver cancer” (69 vs 28 abstracts) and “Hepatotoxicity → Increased proliferation” (20 vs 3 abstracts). The comparable performance for “Cyp2E1 activation”

[45]

Fig. 7. Distribution of biochemical post-translational modification (PTM) triggers across three different query constraints used in the S²CIE system. The first query (Query 1) captures all PTM-related sentences with objects constrained as nouns (15663 statements), the second (Query 2) narrows the scope to gene-type entities (2981 statements), and the third (Query 3) further restricts it to proper nouns (134 statements). The most frequently detected triggers include “reduce,” “phosphorylate,” and “oxidize,” with progressively fewer events captured under stricter constraints.

indicates that limited information available in literature and S²CIE doesn't have access to articles beyond 2021. This temporal limitation can be addressed through periodic index updates incorporating the latest publications.

3.4. Case study 4: extraction of PTMs events guided via BioLink model

To demonstrate S²CIE's applicability beyond chemical toxicity and liver disease, we performed a third case study focused on post-translational modifications (PTMs) a fundamentally different biological domain. This case study showcases S²CIE's domain-agnostic design, where the same query infrastructure can be adapted to extract diverse biological relationships across different mechanistic contexts, from chemical-induced toxicity to fundamental molecular biology processes.

PTMs increase protein diversity and are linked to organismal complexity, with over 650 different PTM types identified and more continuing to be discovered (Zhong, et al., 2023). PTM Homeostasis is vital for human health, as abnormal PTMs can cause protein misfolding, a hallmark of neurodegenerative diseases.

We used S²CIE to extract evidence related to PTMs by using 3 different types of queries to narrow down the search space using the SPO pattern (Fig. 7). The BioLink model (Unni et al., 2022) a standardized biomedical knowledge representation framework, was used to identify appropriate predicates (action verbs) for PTM relationships. For extraction, we defined the rules using verbal trigger patterns in active voice, with triggers specified in wild card format to capture lemmatized forms (Table S4).

We employed a progressive filtering strategy using three queries with increasingly strict constraints (Fig. 7). The first query captures sentences mentioning PTM with the object constrained as "noun" (15663 statements). We further narrowed the constrained to gene-type entities (2981 statements) and finally limited it to proper nouns (134 statements). This progressive narrowing demonstrates S²CIE's flexibility in balancing recall (broad queries) versus precision (strict queries) depending on user requirements.

The extracted statements follow the SPO structure and include entity-type annotations with persistent identifiers (e.g., gene IDs, protein IDs), making them directly compatible with the BioLink standard for biomedical knowledge representation. This compatibility enables the extracted data to be converted into BioLink statements and represented as knowledge graphs (Fig. 1C) using KGX (Knowledge Graph eXchange) (Caufield, et al., 2023), facilitating integration with existing biomedical knowledge resources and computational reasoning systems. While knowledge graph construction is beyond the scope of this work, the retrieved PTM statements (provided in Supplementary Material) demonstrate S²CIE's capability to generate structured, standards-compliant output suitable for downstream knowledge integration.

4. Conclusion and future considerations

In this paper, we introduce S²CIE, a real-time information extraction framework that supports evidence curation for AOP development from biomedical literature. The framework combines domain agnostic syntactic dependency parsing with semantic context to enable flexible extraction of key events, key event relationships, chemical-disease associations, and complex molecular mechanisms. S²CIE rapidly screens 32 million PubMed abstracts with 99 % faster performance than existing tools while delivering high-precision results: 98.79 % precision in chemical-disease extraction across 166 evidence statements for steatosis and cholestasis. Case studies with AOPs 529 and 220 demonstrated S²CIE's capability to retrieve comprehensive event and key event relationship (KER) evidence, respectively. For AOP 220, S²CIE retrieved 1,614 evidence instances (42 % more than AOP-helpFinder) while reducing extraction time from 11 h to average 3.36 min. We also demonstrate large-scale extraction of PTM statements (Section 3.4), highlighting the domain-agnostic nature of the tool and its flexible query

design that allows users to control precision-recall trade-offs, narrow queries maximize precision while broader queries increase recall. S²CIE also enables discovery of previously unknown relationships, for example, a single-line query in Case Study 3.1.1 identified chemicals associated with liver disease without requiring prior knowledge of specific chemical entities. Downstream cheminformatics analyses (Section 3.1.1) and bioinformatics enrichment analyses (Section 3.2) demonstrated in silico applications for knowledge gap identification in chemical risk assessment.

Several areas offer potential for further development to enhance the framework's capabilities. Currently, S²CIE operates on PubMed abstracts, though the framework's architecture supports extension to full-text articles and other biomedical databases. A fundamental challenge for the AOP community is the absence of gold-standard annotated corpora for systematic recall evaluation unlike established NLP domains, toxicology lacks standardized benchmarks. Our expert-based validation reflects current best practices but is currently limited to hepatotoxicity. The ongoing PARC (Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals) (Marx-Stoelting, 2023) project will expand validation to additional toxicological domains and develop community-wide evaluation resources, enabling rigorous cross-tool comparison as text mining adoption increases in regulatory science.

Future work will explore LLM (Large Language Model) integration for mechanistic hypothesis generation, using S²CIE's provenance-supported evidence as high-quality input while maintaining auditability through expert validation. To enhance adaptability, we will develop semi-automated query expansion leveraging domain ontologies and adaptive rules that integrate neural semantic retrieval with interpretable patterns. These enhancements will reduce manual effort and increase recall while preserving the transparency and auditability required for regulatory applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Saurav Kumar: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Shubh Sharma:** Validation, Data curation. **Deepika Deepika:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Judit Biosca-Brull:** Validation, Data curation. **Antonio Moreno:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Vikas Kumar:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Vikas Kumar reports financial support was provided by European Commission.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109986>.

Data availability

We have shared data used for the case study

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